

Ionic Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions of Cadmium Bromide and the Related Heat Data

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The dissociation constants of $\text{CdBr}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Br}^-$ and $\text{CdBr}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ have been determined at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° from e.m.f. of the cell;

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. The e.m.f. of this cell is given by the equation,

$$E = E^\circ + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [\text{H}^+] [\text{Br}^-] f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{Br}^-}$$

The values of $f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{Br}^-}$ at various ionic strengths and E° for the above cell have been found earlier from the study of the cell;

The values of the concentration terms involved in the calculation of dissociation constants are determined from cell (i) with the help of values of $f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{Br}^-}$ at various ionic strengths by the method of successive approximations. With these values of concentrations, the thermodynamic dissociation constant of CdBr^+ multiplied by one thousand has been found to be 7.76, 8.13, 8.75 and 7.55 at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. The corresponding values of thermodynamic dissociation constants of CdBr_2 are 3.98, 5.62, 1.28 and 0.35 respectively. The heats of ionisation (ΔH) of $\text{CdBr}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Br}^-$ and $\text{CdBr}_2 = \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ found by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$ are 800 ± 300 cal/mole and $-22,000 \pm 2,000$ cal/mole respectively. The values of ΔF for $\text{CdBr}_2 = \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ and $\text{CdBr}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Br}^-$ at 25° are -150 cal. and 2808 cal. respectively. The corresponding values of ΔS are -73 cal./degree and -6.7 cal./degree respectively.

ASSUMING the first stage of dissociation, $\text{CdBr}_2 \rightarrow \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ to be complete in very dilute solution, Riley and Gallafent¹ found the dissociation constant of $\text{CdBr}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Br}^-$ from the potentiometric titrations to be 6.8×10^{-3} at 25°. An extensive study of the thermodynamic behaviour of cadmium bromide in aqueous solutions was made by Bates² from e.m.f. measurements of the cell;

from 5°, to 40°. He found the dissociation constant of CdBr^+ ion multiplied by one thousand, to be 6.0, at 5°, 6.5 at 10°, 15°, and 20° and 7.0 at 25°, 30°, 35° and 40°. He assumed that the activity coefficient of completely dissociated part of cadmium bromide is equal to that of barium chloride. No change in the value of dissociation constant from 10 to 20 and from 25° to 40° did not appear to be reasonable to us. Cadmium bromide in a salt of weak base and strong acid. Therefore, it is bound to be hydrolysed in aqueous solutions. It was thought worthwhile to redetermine the dissociation constants of $\text{CdBr}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Br}^-$ as well as of $\text{CdBr}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ by eliminating the possibility of hydrolysis also.

A cell of the type;

has been employed to determine the dissociation constant of both $\text{CdBr}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Br}^-$ and $\text{CdBr}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35°. Hydrolysis has been eliminated on account of the presence of free hydrogen ions from hydrobromic acid. Since the solubilities of quinhydrone and silver bromide are very small, there is negligible if any liquid junction potential between the solutions in the half elements and the solution in the bridge. The bridge is interposed to avoid direct mixing of quinhydrone and silver bromide.

Experimental

A stock solution of cadmium bromide was prepared by dissolving cadmium bromide (G.R.) in dilute hydrobromic acid. The amounts of cadmium and total bromide present in the stock solution were estimated gravimetrically (by oxine³) and volumetrically (by Volhard's⁴ method) respectively. So the stoichiometric concentration of CdBr_2 and HBr

in the stock solution could be calculated. Experimental solutions were prepared by adding additional amount of standard hydrobromic acid⁵, where ever necessary, and then diluting to appropriate volume at the temperature at which the experiment was carried out. Double distilled water was used in the preparation of all the solutions. All concentrations are expressed in gram moles/litre. The silver-silver bromide electrode was prepared as recommended by Bates⁶. The electrode vessels and bridges were similar to those of Prasad and Co-workers⁷. The cells were set up in the same way as done earlier⁵. The temperature of the air thermostat was constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Measurements were made with a Bajaj vernier Potentiometer which gave the same readings as Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer. Duplicate experiments were performed in each case and the duplicates generally agreed within ± 0.1 mv. In some cases the differences went up to 0.15 mv. The recorded e.m.f. values are the mean of the duplicate. The symbol $[]_T$ represents stoichiometric concentrations. Concentrations range have been so chosen that the ionic strength even in rough calculation did not exceed 0.1.

Discussion

The e.m.f. of the cell ;

is given by the equation,

$$E = E^\circ + \frac{2.30259 RT}{F} \log[\text{H}^+][\text{Br}^-] f_H f_{Br} \dots (1)$$

and

$$-\log f_H f_{Br} = \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu \dots (2)$$

In the above equation 'A' is the constant of Debye-Huckel equation and 'B' is found from the study of the cell reported earlier⁵. The values of 'A' and 'B' at various temperatures are given below :

	5°	15°	25°	35°
A	0.4921	0.5002	0.5092	0.5190
B	0.5618	0.5478	0.5274	0.5152

Assuming that the first stage of dissociation $\text{CdBr}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$ is complete in very dilute solution the only ions present in this solution can be Cd^{++} , CdBr^+ , Br^- and H^+ , and hence the ionic strength of the solution will be given by the equation,

$$\mu = 2[\text{Cd}^{++}] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{CdBr}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{Br}^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] \dots (3)$$

The various concentration terms are found as explained in the case of cadmium chloride⁸ and are given in tables 1 to 4.

The dissociation constant (K_2) of CdBr^+ is given by

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{Cd}^{++}][\text{Br}^-]}{[\text{CdBr}^+]} \times \frac{f_{\text{Cd}^{++}} f_{\text{Br}^-}}{f_{\text{CdBr}^+}} = K_{A(2)} \frac{f_{\text{Cd}^{++}} f_{\text{Br}^-}}{f_{\text{CdBr}^+}}$$

New applying the equation,

$$-\log f_i = \frac{AZi^2\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - Bi\mu,$$

TABLE 1

Temperature—5°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[Br ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdBr ⁺] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T					
0.004	0.004	0.38729	2.04	10.04	1.96	12.08
0.005	0.005	0.39718	3.25	12.35	2.65	14.70
0.006	0.006	0.40505	2.48	14.48	3.52	16.96
0.007	0.007	0.41176	2.61	16.61	4.39	19.22
0.008	0.008	0.41771	2.86	18.86	5.14	21.72
0.009	0.009	0.42281	2.93	20.93	6.07	23.86
0.010	0.010	0.42745	3.07	23.07	6.93	26.14

TABLE 2

Temperature—15°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[Br ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdBr ⁺] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T					
0.004	0.004	0.37470	1.94	9.94	2.06	11.88
0.005	0.005	0.38511	2.32	12.32	2.68	14.64
0.006	0.006	0.39336	2.52	14.52	3.48	17.04
0.007	0.007	0.40027	2.64	16.64	4.36	19.28
0.008	0.008	0.40634	2.81	18.81	5.19	21.62
0.009	0.009	0.41179	3.06	21.06	5.94	24.12
0.010	0.010	0.41645	3.06	23.06	6.94	26.12

TABLE 3

Temperature—25°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Cd ⁺⁺] $\times 10^3$	[Br ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[CdBr ⁺] $\times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T					
0.004	0.004	0.36311	2.18	10.18	1.82	12.36
0.005	0.005	0.37358	2.46	12.46	2.54	14.92
0.006	0.006	0.38213	2.70	14.70	3.30	17.40
0.007	0.007	0.38939	2.95	16.95	4.05	19.90
0.008	0.008	0.39566	3.15	19.15	4.85	22.30
0.009	0.009	0.40110	3.25	21.25	5.75	24.50
0.010	0.010	0.40600	3.37	23.37	6.63	26.74

TABLE 4

Temperature—35°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Cd ⁺⁺] $\times 10^3$	[Br ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[CdBr ⁺] $\times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T					
0.004	0.004	0.35100	1.65	9.65	2.35	11.30
0.005	0.005	0.36242	2.13	12.13	2.87	14.26
0.006	0.006	0.37134	2.38	14.38	3.62	16.76
0.007	0.007	0.37875	2.50	16.50	4.50	19.00
0.008	0.008	0.38516	2.60	18.60	5.40	21.20
0.009	0.009	0.39083	2.68	20.68	6.32	23.36
0.010	0.010	0.39592	2.77	22.77	7.23	25.54

We get,

$$\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_2 - B'\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

The value of $K_{A(2)}$ is next calculated from the values of [Cd⁺⁺], [Br⁻] and [CdBr⁺] given in tables 1 to 4. The value of K_2 and B' are found by graphical plots (Fig. 1).

It may be noted that the above scheme works only up to 0.01M cadmium bromide solutions. Tables 1 to 4 cover this range. When the concentration of CdBr₂ exceeds 0.01, the assumption that the first stage of dissociation CdBr₂ \rightarrow CdBr⁺ + Br⁻ is complete may not be true and the method of evaluation of K_2 as shown above may fail.

Under such circumstances, it is more reasonable to assume a scheme of dissociation shown below :

Even when the undissociated CdBr₂ is present, the only ions present in the solution are Br⁻, Cd⁺⁺, CdBr⁺ and H⁺. Hence the ionic strength is given by equation (3). Following the same kind of argument as in the case of cadmium chloride⁸, the values of the concentrations of Br⁻, CdBr⁺ and CdBr₂, and value of μ were calculated and are given in tables 5 to 8.

TABLE 5

Temperature—5°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Br ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[CdBr ⁺] $\times 10^3$	[Cd ⁺⁺] $\times 10^3$	[CdBr ₂] $\times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T						
0.020	0.020	0.45732	42.55	15.71	3.42	0.87	45.97
0.022	0.022	0.46134	46.11	17.31	3.40	1.29	49.51
0.024	0.024	0.46504	49.68	18.95	3.37	1.68	53.05
0.026	0.025	0.46841	53.11	20.47	3.32	2.21	56.43
0.028	0.028	0.47147	56.35	21.83	3.26	2.91	59.61
0.030	0.030	0.47428	59.43	23.05	3.19	3.76	62.62

TABLE 6

Temperature—15°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Br ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdBr ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdBr ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T						
0.020	0.020	0.44750	42.81	16.30	3.26	0.44	46.07
0.022	0.022	0.45162	46.30	17.90	3.20	0.90	49.50
0.024	0.024	0.45545	49.90	19.61	3.15	1.24	53.05
0.026	0.026	0.45893	53.34	21.20	3.07	1.73	56.41
0.028	0.028	0.46222	56.92	22.91	3.01	2.07	59.92
0.030	0.030	0.46513	60.04	24.22	2.91	2.87	62.95

TABLE 7

Temperature—25°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr		E in volt.	[Br ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdBr ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdBr ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
[CdBr ₂] _T	[HBr] _T						
0.020	0.020	0.43787	43.03	15.16	3.94	0.90	46.98
0.022	0.022	0.44227	46.85	16.93	3.96	1.11	50.81
0.024	0.024	0.44622	50.48	18.58	3.95	1.47	54.43
0.026	0.026	0.44987	54.10	20.24	3.93	1.83	58.03
0.028	0.028	0.45329	57.78	21.98	3.90	2.12	61.68
0.030	0.030	0.45638	61.18	23.48	3.85	2.67	65.03

TABLE 8

Temperature—35°

Mixture of CdBr ₂ & HBr			E in volt.	[Br ⁻] × 10 ³	[CdBr ⁺] × 10 ³	[Cd ⁺⁺] × 10 ³	[CdBr ₂] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
[CdBr ₂] _T	W	[HBr] _T						
0.020	0.020	0.42830	41.03	15.63	2.70	1.67	43.73	
0.022	0.022	0.43281	44.61	17.35	2.63	2.02	47.24	
0.024	0.024	0.43686	48.02	18.92	2.55	2.53	50.57	
0.026	0.026	0.44064	51.51	20.57	2.47	2.96	53.98	
0.028	0.028	0.44413	54.93	22.16	2.39	3.45	57.32	
0.030	0.030	0.44742	58.43	23.84	2.30	3.86	60.73	

Now,

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{CdBr}^+][\text{Br}^-]}{[\text{CdBr}_2]} \times f_{\text{CdBr}} f_{\text{Br}}$$

because the activity coefficient of undissociated cadmium bromide can be taken to be unity.

Writing

$$K_{A(1)} \text{ for } \frac{[\text{CdBr}^+][\text{Br}^-]}{[\text{CdBr}_2]}$$

we get,

$$\log K_{A(1)} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - B''\mu \quad \dots (5)$$

Now K_1 is found from the values of [CdBr⁺], [Br⁻] and [CdBr₂] from tables 5 to 8. The values of K_1 is also found by graphical plots (Fig. 2).

Both in case of figures 1 and 2 extrapolation is long. This is so because the two straight line equations are applicable within certain ionic strengths only.

Equilibrium constants are determined on the molarity scale these days. The present work has been done on molarity scale. The graphically determined K_1 and K_2 are on the molarity scale. The relation between the two comes out to be, K_1 (molarity) = ρK_1 (molarity); K_2 (molarity) = ρK_2 (molarity), when ρ = density of water. Slight change in the value of B' and B'' does not affect the results. Hence B' and B'' can be taken to be the same on the two scales. Further ΔH° has been taken to be equal to ΔH . There is very slight change in the values of ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° on the two scales. The change is within experimental error.

The value of ΔH° has been found as explained earlier⁸. The value of ΔC° at 25° has been found from $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$ and that of ΔS° from $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$. The necessary values are given in Tables 9 and 10.

Fig. 1. Equation : $\text{Log } K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \text{Log } K_2 - B'\mu$
L.H.S.E. plotted against μ .

Fig. 2. Equation : $\text{Log } K_{A(1)} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \text{Log } K_1 - B''\mu$;
Plot of L.H.S.E. against μ .

TABLE 9

	5°	15°	25°	35°
K_1 (molarity)	3.98	5.62	1.29	0.35
K_1 (molality)	3.98	5.63	1.29	0.35
B''	19.60	19.62	8.94	3.36
$K_2 \times 10^3$ (molarity)	7.76	8.13	8.75	7.55
$K_2 \times 10^3$ (molality)	7.76	8.14	8.78	7.60
B'	5.89	7.19	5.45	8.86

TABLE 10

Reaction	ΔH° in cal.	ΔG° at 25° in cal.	ΔS° at 25° in cal./degree
$\text{CdBr}_2 = \text{CdBr}^+ + \text{Br}^-$	$-22,000 \pm 2000$	-150	-73
$\text{CdBr}^+ = \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{Br}^-$	800 ± 300	2808	-6.7

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